

Workshop Report: Generative AI in the Digital Economy

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Presenters: Christopher Burr, Christopher Thomas, Florimond Houssiau, Cailean Osborne

This report is an overview and summary of “Generative AI in the Digital Economy” workshop, which was co-located with CADE 2024. The workshop followed a blended format. First half was a hybrid participation with an in-person expert panel and online invited speakers. The second half of the workshop focused on “trust” and “trustworthiness” terms. This report presents the panel findings, invited speaker presentation overviews and our discussion around “trustworthiness.”

Highlights

- Generative AI, particularly large language models (LLMs), shows promise in financial services for tasks such as compliance checks, marketing, translation, and customer interaction.
- Ensuring the transparency and explainability of AI-driven decisions is crucial for building trust with stakeholders, including customers, regulators, and internal auditors. Potential solutions include chain-of-thought prompting and "reasoning and acting (ReAct)" methods.
- Privacy is a major concern. LLMs trained on vast datasets may inadvertently capture sensitive customer information, potentially leading to exposure. The use of synthetic data and techniques like private AI offer potential solutions to mitigate privacy risks.
- Synthetic data can address data asymmetry issues, providing opportunities for smaller businesses to develop solutions without accessing sensitive data.
- Notable successes include using LLMs to train customer service operators by generating realistic scenarios and generating personalized marketing materials with rapid feedback analysis.

Challenges

- Many businesses struggle to understand the capabilities, limitations, and appropriate uses of generative AI, leading to misapplication and potential risks.
- LLMs' tendency to generate inaccurate information ("hallucination") and hard-to-predict prompt-based attacks poses challenges, particularly in contexts requiring high accuracy.
- Lack of training on effectively and securely prompting and using LLMs poses a significant obstacle for wider adoption.

Next Steps

- Establishing industry standards and best practices for developing, deploying, and auditing generative AI systems in finance is crucial.
- Further research into more robust and comprehensive explainability methods tailored for financial applications is needed.
- Universities and private institutions should offer specialized training programs to equip professionals with the skills to navigate generative AI's complexities.
- Fostering open-source AI development could enhance transparency, inclusivity, and innovation in the field.

Introduction

The digital economy refers to economic activities that rely on digital technologies, such as the internet, mobile devices, and digital platforms, to create, distribute, and consume goods and services. It encompasses various sectors including e-commerce, online banking, digital marketing, and telecommuting, enabling businesses and individuals to conduct transactions, communication, and commerce electronically, leading to increased efficiency, innovation, and globalization of markets.

Machine learning (ML) systems have become integral components of the digital economy and have been revolutionising various tasks such as financial modelling, security analysis, fraud detection and customer interaction. From linear models utilised in the scoring systems to neural nets in biometrics for customer authentication, these different ML applications powered an extensive array of indispensable applications in the digital economy.

In the past decade, generative AI has become an interest to many considering their advanced capabilities in processing large volumes of data and generating plausible outputs. Their ability to demonstrate success in these different tasks can be bound to two properties: The scale of the training data and the size of the model architecture.

Based on the output modalities, generative AI models can be categorised as language models, image models, video models, multi-modal models, etc. While language models excel in text-based tasks such as language translation, summarization, and information processing, an image model can generate thousands of synthetic face data which can help us to develop face biometric systems in a privacy-preserving way. The multi-modal production capabilities of Generative AI also supported practitioners in achieving privacy, security and productivity in application development by demonstrating significant improvements in synthetic data production, unstructured data understanding, and multi-modal data interpretation.

The opportunities presented by generative AI and LLMs are vast. Currently, businesses of varied sizes and sectors have started using these models to power up their products before comprehensively understanding the nature of data and models. They leverage these technologies for analysing complex unstructured data, generating insights, customer engagement, or automation of repetitive tasks.

Public Communication and Customer Engagement	Financial Service Safety	Financial Insight Generation	Financing and Investment Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Financial CommunicationCustomer service	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Detecting and preventing fraudProduct developmentRisk assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Market surveillanceMarket insights and reportsBusiness finance data insightsPersonal investment insightsGeneration of aggregate reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Investment bankingTreasury optimisationPrivate equity and venture capital strategy developmentAsset allocation

However, alongside these opportunities, challenges persist. In this dynamic and sensitive environment, proactively incorporating security, privacy and fairness considerations is crucial. For example, biases inherent in training data can

perpetuate societal inequalities and undermine the fairness of AI systems. Additionally, the resource-intensive nature of training and deploying advanced AI models poses scalability issues for smaller organizations. Further, their data and model size and black-box structure raised concerns over the safe integration of these applications. Despite the sustained effort on developing robust, secure, and fair language models, researchers and practitioners still struggle to achieve these characteristics that build up safety. This is partly due to the complex nature of these concepts, and the decentralized efforts of design, development and assessment groups.

Data-related risks	Model complexity-related risks	Social behaviours and Human Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bias• Privacy• Data transparency and security• Violation of intellectual property	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of explainability• Reasoning errors• Susceptibility to various attacks	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Alignment• Information hallucination• Toxic linguistic• Environmental impacts• Open vs close source impacts

Generative AI has the potential to revolutionize the digital economy by enhancing accessibility and usability of several financial services. However, the challenges associated with security, privacy, fairness, and resource intensiveness should also be acknowledged. This document presents an overview of these opportunities and challenges with the notes from our panel discussion and invited speaker presentations.

Overview of the Panel Discussion

Panel Members: Carsten Maple, University of Warwick, The Alan Turing Institute, Andrew Elliott, University of Glasgow, The Alan Turing Institute, Marie Briere, Amundi Investment Institute, Université Libre de Bruxelles & Paris Dauphine PSL University, Michela Iezzi, Banca d'Italia

Moderator: Alpay Sabuncuoglu, The Alan Turing Institute

Challenges overview. What are the primary challenges businesses face when integrating generative AI into their operations?

- One of the foremost challenges is comprehending what generative AI truly entails. The term "AI" encompasses a broad range of technologies, including shallow/light models and deep models. Many businesses struggle with this fundamental understanding, which is essential for effectively leveraging the technology rather than simply following industry trends.
- Deploying generative AI systems requires substantial computational resources. Businesses must recognize the responsibilities associated with using such technologies, including the financial and infrastructural investments needed. This includes ensuring that their AI initiatives align with their broader organizational goals and capabilities.
- Companies must consider their environmental sustainability and governance commitments when integrating AI. Generative AI models can be resource-intensive, and organizations need to weigh their use against sustainability goals. Using the right tool for the right task, while considering alternative, less resource-intensive options, is a critical aspect of responsible AI integration.

Find a more detailed overview of challenges in our previous published "The Impact of LLMs in Financial Services" report: <https://www.turing.ac.uk/news/publications/impact-large-language-models-finance-towards-trustworthy-adoption>

Explainability. How can businesses in the finance sector ensure that the decision-making processes powered by generative AI are transparent and explainable to stakeholders, including regulators, customers, and internal auditors?

- Trust in AI outputs is crucial, both for internal users and clients. Generating trust involves providing clear, understandable explanations for AI decisions. This is particularly challenging due to the inherent complexity of AI systems and the biases they may introduce. For example, biases present in LLMs can mirror human behavioural biases, complicating the task of generating trustworthy and aligned outputs.
- LLMs can exhibit biases similar to those found in human decision-making, which can lead to outputs that are not fully aligned with users' interests. This misalignment is especially problematic in client interactions, such as when providing financial advice. Ensuring that AI outputs are in the client's best interest requires rigorous testing and validation before real-world implementation.
- Several methods are currently employed to enhance the explainability of AI systems:
 - o Post-Hoc Explanations: These involve feature attribution, where words or tokens are treated as features, and the contribution of each feature to the model's output is assessed. Techniques such as gradient-based methods are used to provide these explanations. However, these methods demand significant computational resources and may not always deliver the type of explanations desired.
 - o Chain of Thought Prompting: This method uses LLMs as reasoning engines, providing explicit reasoning steps that lead to the final answer. By outlining these reasoning steps, the AI system becomes more interpretable.
 - o Reasoning and Acting (ReAct) Methods: These methods involve LLMs generating both reasoning traces and task-specific actions. This approach helps in understanding the reasoning steps and provides detailed explanations of how the final result was derived.
- Understanding what constitutes a "good" explanation is critical. According to research by Miller, effective explanations should have the following properties: (Selectivity) Explanations should focus on the most important or abnormal elements, as these are typically of most interest to humans. (Contractiveness) Explanations should clarify why a particular event happened instead of an alternative outcome. (Social and Contextual Relevance) Explanations should be tailored to the needs and contexts of the users, making them more meaningful and understandable.
- The field of explainable AI is still evolving, with many methods being works in progress. Continued research is necessary to develop and refine techniques that provide clear, meaningful explanations that meet the needs of all stakeholders.

Privacy. What are the primary privacy concerns associated with using generative AI in financial services, and how can businesses address these concerns to protect sensitive customer data?

- Generative AI models are trained on extensive datasets that may include sensitive customer data. During the training phase, there is a risk that this sensitive information could be inadvertently incorporated into the model. Once embedded, this data could potentially be exposed through the model's outputs.
- During the inference phase, where the AI model is used to generate outputs based on new inputs, there is a risk of sensitive information being inferred or leaked. This is especially critical when dealing with unstructured data or large datasets, which may contain hidden sensitive information.
- Financial institutions may integrate data from external sources, such as social media, which does not reside on their infrastructure. This integration can lead to privacy concerns, as customers may feel uncomfortable

knowing that their financial institutions are using such data. The aggregation and use of external data can potentially expose personal information that customers did not intend to share with financial institutions.

- To mitigate privacy concerns, businesses can implement private AI solutions, which involve stricter controls over data access and usage. These solutions ensure that sensitive data is processed in a way that limits exposure and adheres to privacy regulations.
- Using synthetic data, which is artificially generated data that mimics the statistical properties of real data, can help protect sensitive information. By training and prompting AI models with synthetic data, businesses can reduce the risk of exposing actual customer data.
- Implementing robust data anonymization techniques can help in protecting customer identities by removing personally identifiable information (PII) from datasets used for training and inference. Additionally, encrypting data both at rest and in transit ensures that unauthorized parties cannot access sensitive information.
- Ensuring that all AI-related operations are conducted on secure infrastructure is crucial. Financial institutions should maintain strict control over their data environments, ensuring that sensitive data is not accessible to unauthorized users or external entities.
- Adhering to regulatory requirements and establishing strong data governance frameworks are essential for protecting customer data. Regular audits, compliance checks, and transparent data handling practices can help in maintaining trust and ensuring that privacy standards are met.
- Communicating openly with customers about how their data is used and protected can help alleviate privacy concerns. Providing clear information on data usage policies, and ensuring that customers have control over their data, fosters trust and transparency.

Synthetic Data. Currently, data asymmetry between big and small firms in financial sector is a huge issue. It was also an [open CFI](#) by FCA. Could recent developments in the synthetic data generation domain help businesses to compete with big businesses? How can small businesses leverage these techniques?

- Data asymmetry poses a significant challenge in the financial sector, especially between large and small firms. Larger institutions have extensive datasets, allowing them to derive valuable insights and maintain a competitive edge. In contrast, smaller businesses and academic researchers often lack access to such vast amounts of data. Recent advancements in synthetic data generation offer promising solutions to mitigate this disparity.
- Synthetic data generation techniques enable the creation of realistic and high-quality data that mimics the statistical properties of real-world data. This can provide smaller firms with the datasets they need for training models, conducting research, and developing new financial products and services.
- Synthetic data can be generated without containing any real personal or sensitive information, thus mitigating privacy concerns. This allows for the safe sharing and usage of data, enabling small businesses to collaborate more effectively with partners and regulators.
- Acquiring and maintaining large datasets can be expensive. Synthetic data generation offers a cost-effective alternative, enabling small firms to access diverse and extensive datasets without the high costs associated with data collection and storage.
- With synthetic data, small businesses can experiment with new models and algorithms, perform simulations, and test scenarios without the risk of exposing sensitive customer data. This fosters a culture of innovation and rapid development.
- Small businesses can leverage open-source synthetic data generation tools and models, which are often available at lower costs or for free. These tools can help them create datasets tailored to their specific needs.

- Regulatory bodies like the FCA are increasingly recognizing the importance of synthetic data. Small businesses can engage with these institutions to gain access to regulatory-approved synthetic datasets and participate in collaborative initiatives aimed at promoting data accessibility and innovation.
- Synthetic data can be used to train smaller, more specialized AI models that are designed for specific tasks within the financial sector. These models can offer competitive performance while being more resource-efficient compared to large-scale models used by big firms.
- When using synthetic data, small businesses must prioritize privacy and security. This includes implementing robust threat modelling, understanding the limitations of synthetic data, and ensuring compliance with relevant data protection regulations.
- The field of synthetic data generation is rapidly evolving. Small businesses should stay informed about the latest developments and methodologies to continuously enhance their data strategies and maintain a competitive edge.

Successful Case Studies. Can you discuss a successful case study where generative AI significantly improved a business process or service in your organization/one of the organisations you work with? What lessons were learned from the implementation of generative AI in this case, and how can they inform future applications?

In the financial sector, the application of LLMs has been cautious yet steadily growing. Successful applications include:

- Back Office and Middle Office Operations: Some organizations have already employed LLMs to automate compliance checks, ensuring that regulatory mentions were correctly included in documents presented to clients. This reduced manual review time and minimized errors. LLMs are also integrated to write automatic reports, particularly in the asset management industry, and for tasks such as translation and summarization. This streamlined operations and allowed staff to focus on more strategic activities.
- Client Interaction: Developing chatbots for handling simple client queries, such as password requests. While not yet used for providing financial advice, this application demonstrated potential for enhancing customer service through efficient, automated interactions.
- Research Assistance: LLMs have been utilised to build sentiment analysis tools and identify entities in financial news. This aided portfolio managers and researchers in making informed decisions. Researchers also benefited from LLMs as coding assistants and tools for searching and testing various hypotheses, significantly speeding up the research process.

Lessons learned for the adoption, integration, usage and maintenance:

- Management should carefully evaluate the costs of implementing AI, such as computational expenses related to token usage, against the potential savings in labour costs.
- Implementing ethical walls between departments ensured that confidential information was only accessible to authorized personnel. Maintaining security and privacy standards was essential to build trust in the organisation and for the clients.
- Ensuring personal data protection and establishing protocols for securely handling sensitive information were critical to the AI deployment.
- There was a significant need for formal training on how to use LLMs effectively and securely. The organization recognized the value of training programs to enhance employee skills in AI usage.
- The organizations should be mindful of the carbon footprint associated with running large AI models and balanced this with the financial costs of implementation. Sustainable practices and efficient resource management should be prioritized.

Despite the challenges, future applications are expected to continue on areas where AI can provide clear efficiency gains and cost savings. Prioritizing applications based on a thorough cost-benefit analysis will ensure sustainable growth.

Overview of the Invited Speaker Presentations

Presenter: Christopher Burr, The Alan Turing Institute

Trustworthy and Ethical Assurance: An open-source and community-based approach to assurance

The project focuses on the trustworthy and ethical assurance of digital twins. Although the current focus is not on digital twins in financial services, it's important to note the potential applicability in this sector. Digital twins can indeed be developed for financial services and the logical entities that constitute financial systems. The main question in ethical assurance is "How should researchers and developers provide assurance that some ethical goal has been achieved over the course of a designing, developing, and deploying a data-driven technology, such as a machine learning model or AI system?". In his presentation, Christopher introduced the [Trustworthy and Ethical Assurance \(TEA\) platform](#), which allows project teams and stakeholders to define and explore assurance cases in a systematic manner.

Presenter: Christopher Thomas, The Alan Turing Institute

Standards in the context of generative AI

Standardization for AI is crucial as it provides common, repeatable rules developed through consensus-building processes. International standards for AI play a vital role in operationalizing ethical and regulatory guidance, ensuring quality and safety assurance, and facilitating knowledge and technology transfer. They promote interoperability, enhance market access, and establish links to other governance mechanisms. Moreover, they enable third-party assurance and certification, support designated and harmonized standards, and are essential for UKCA/CE marking. Through these mechanisms, standardization helps create a cohesive and reliable framework for the development and deployment of AI technologies globally. The AI Standards hub page: <https://aistandardshub.org/>

Presenter: Florimond Houssiau, Tune Insight SA

TAPAS: Toolbox for Adversarial Privacy Auditing of Synthetic Data

TAPAS aims to build a comprehensive toolbox of attacks to evaluate Synthetic Data Generation (SDG) models. This general-purpose toolkit supports diverse data formats, including time-series and networks, and accommodates a range of threat models for real-world situations, ensuring its applicability to any SDG model. As an open-source project, TAPAS welcomes contributions from the community, fostering collaboration and continuous improvement. For more information and to contribute, visit TAPAS on GitHub: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/tapas>.

Presenter: Cailean Osborne, Oxford Internet Institute

Key insights from latest research on open-source AI

The increasing number of repositories advertised as "open source" AI models lacks a consistent definition. Many components beyond model weights are not released, which hampers transparency, reproducibility, safety, and usability. There is also misuse of open-source licenses on non-software components, the creation of new licenses with restrictions, and instances of illegally converted licenses. To address these issues, the Model Openness Framework has been

developed as a systematic methodology to evaluate the completeness and openness of open models based on open science principles. This framework features a three-tiered classification system with open license recommendations for 17 code, data, and documentation components in open models. For model developers, such as researchers and developers, the framework provides guidance to enhance model transparency and reproducibility while allowing permissive usage. For model consumers, including enterprise users, it offers clarity on which models are suitable for commercial use. See the paper: <https://arxiv.org/html/2405.13058v2>

Presenter: Alpay Sabuncuoglu, The Alan Turing Institute

Proactive Monitoring of AI Fairness

The Fairness Monitoring tool is designed to enable proactive fairness assessments during the development of AI systems. Its main goal is to help developers evaluate and mitigate potential biases in AI models early in the development process, integrating fairness considerations into Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) workflows. The tool accomplishes this by providing methods for evaluating and mitigating fairness issues at various stages, including data processing, algorithm selection, and user interaction design. By integrating fairness checks into the development pipeline, it helps ensure that the AI models deployed are as unbiased and fair as possible, thus enhancing transparency and accountability. For more detailed information, you can explore the project on GitHub: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/fairness-monitoring>

Discussion: Trust and Trustworthiness

The [recently published guidance on AI assurance](#) state that the processes followed throughout the assurance potentially support building confidence in AI systems. They do this by measuring and evaluating standardized and accessible evidence, in other words, reliable evidence, regarding the capabilities. By promoting trust through effective communication with stakeholders and ensuring the trustworthiness of AI systems, AI assurance is crucial for the responsible development and deployment of AI. This, in turn, unlocks the economic and social benefits that AI systems can offer.

Regarding the use of AI, building trustworthy applications requires gathering all the reliable evidence across multiple components of trustworthiness. [NIST AI RME](#) defines “trustworthy” AI with seven components: validity and reliability, safety, security and resilience, accountability and transparency, explainability and interpretability, privacy enhancement, and fair management of harmful bias. Each of these characteristics involves numerous subcomponents, contributing to the complexity of achieving a shared understanding and realisation of truly trustworthy AI.

This workshop gathered researchers and practitioners with various domain interests from industry and academia. Even the research presented from diverse application areas could only scratch a surface to achieve assurance regarding “trustworthy” AI assurance. The presented work is complementary to each other to build an effective monitoring and evaluation of ML pipelines against common safety challenges. For example, Burr’s open-source assurance tool can help businesses structure their assurance processes, while Sabuncuoglu’s monitoring tool can provide evidence for the fairness component. Then TAPAS can provide another evidence to evaluate and mitigate potential privacy-related challenges. Establishing a continuous and proactive flow to audit the development and deployment process from multiple perspectives and organise effective workflows for multidisciplinary teams is essential to build effective “justified” trust.